

Prime Number Representation of Fields in Stationary 2T F-Theoretic Manifolds

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Abstract

2T product 13-orbifolds $(O, \gamma) = (G, g) \otimes (M, g_E)$, where G is a compact elliptically fibered Calabi-Yau 4-orbifold (8-manifold uncompact) with special holonomy and M a 2T Einstein manifold, may serve as geometric models for compactified 13-D F-Theory with signature $(11, 2)$. Invoking stationarity with respect to the curvature on (O, γ) in which $\gamma \propto \mathcal{R}_O$, where \mathcal{R}_O is the Ricci flow tensor, implies that $\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial^2 \gamma'}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial^2 \gamma'}{\partial \tau^2} = 0$ in the Euler-Lagrange operator expressed as a chained partial derivative with respect to the 13-D 2T coordinate $\mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{x}, t, \tau)$. The metric tensor variational amounts $\partial \gamma$ and $\partial \gamma'$ are respectfully, the last factors in the terms of the chained partial derivatives in the Euler-Lagrange operator. By manifold stationarity, $\partial \gamma = 0$. Discretizing $\partial \gamma$, one obtains finite sum approximations using incremental variations $\partial \gamma_i, i = 1, \dots, N$ for some $N \in \mathbb{N}$ where $\partial \gamma \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \partial \gamma_i$. The N -tuples of variations $\{\partial \gamma_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N}$, can then be categorized modulo a signed prime integer valued net variation for $\partial \gamma$. One can find the modulo groups of N -tuples that obtain each net variation value, denoted by $v_{\text{net}}(m)$, for the m -th such prime value. An integer-valued functional $v_{\text{tot}}(m, n, K)$, showed by induction, can then be developed to obtain the number of distinct N -tuples that result in a particular modulo signed net variation value $v_{\text{net}}(m)$. Denoting the set of net prime variations by $\mathbb{N}\mathbb{P}\mathbb{V}$, it is then claimed that each net variation corresponds to a distinct 2T Dp-brane field. Then, for a given $m \in \mathbb{N}$, the total net variation, $v_{\text{tot}}(m, n, K)$, represents a random 2T Dp-brane field metric tensor curvature variation from the N -tuples $\{\partial \gamma_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N}$, approximating $\partial \gamma$, and the ratio $\alpha_v(m, n, K) = \frac{v_{\text{tot}}(m-1, n, K)}{v_{\text{tot}}(m, n, K)}$, its coupling constant parameter.

Introduction

M-Theory unifies the representation of the five string theories utilizing dualities (T-duality and S-duality) or symmetry operators between them via mappings in the moduli space of vacua [17]. F-Theory, in turn, is M-Theory realized on a two-torus manifold (T2) with a vanishing volume $v \rightarrow 0$ with $\mathcal{N} = 1$ spacetime SUSY [5]. F-Theory is a GUT model. Compact elliptically fibered Calabi-Yau 4-fold orbifolds, which are uncompactified 8-D Riemannian orbifolds with special holonomy serve as structures for compactification spaces [7] [10] [8] [6] [5]. F-theory manifolds may be viewed as uncompactified product manifolds:

$$(O, \gamma) = (G, g) \otimes (M, g_E) \quad (1)$$

with signature (11, 2) where G is a elliptically fibered Calabi-Yau 4-orbifold with metric tensor g (8-D uncompactified manifold), and M a 2T Einstein manifold with metric tensor g_E , with signature (3, 2), are models for 13-D 2T F-Theory [1] [16]. In 2T General Relativity (GR), Einstein manifolds (M, g_E) with signature (3, 2) model the relativistic 2T spacetime universe. Einstein manifolds are Lorentz manifolds where $\mathcal{R}_E = \eta g_E$, where \mathcal{R}_E is its Einstein Ricci tensor, g_E , its metric tensor, and $\eta \in \mathbb{C}$ [9] [4]. Kähler-Einstein manifolds generalize this structure to complex manifolds. Compactification spaces in F-Theory require Calabi-Yau 4-orbifolds. In M/F-Theory, the manifest indivisible object is the Dp -brane. Dp -branes are generalized blobs of dimension p with Dirichlet boundary conditions satisfied on the ends of open strings localized on them, with p -volume on the order of the p -D Planck volume v_p^p , that sweep out via world-volume field content in spacetime to subsume or intersect with other objects such as the ends of open strings. For the 13-D manifold F-Theory model, $p \leq 13$. 2T Dp -branes contain an extra time and compacted space dimension.

Consider the differentiable Lagrangian operator $L : T_O \rightarrow O$ where T_O is the phase space of velocities of O (tangent space). In (O, γ) , one may form the Lagrangian operator $L(\Psi, \Psi', t)$, where $\Psi(z) \in O$ is the positional field at $\mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{x}, t, \tau)$ and \mathbf{x} has 11-D coordinates. The Euler-Lagrange equation is then expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \Psi} - \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t})} \right) - \frac{d}{d\tau} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \tau})} \right) - \frac{d}{d\mathbf{x}} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{x}})} \right) = 0 \quad (2)$$

By repeated partial differentiation with respect to the involved fields and field metric tensors (i.e. Ricci flow and curvature field metric tensors), one can express (2) as the chained partial differential equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial L}{\partial \Psi} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathcal{R}_O} \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t})} \frac{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t})}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathcal{R}} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}}{\partial t^2} \\ & - \frac{\partial L}{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \tau})} \frac{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \tau})}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathcal{R}} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}}{\partial \tau^2} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{x}})} \frac{\partial (\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{x}})}{\partial \mathcal{R}} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^2} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{R} is the Ricci flow tensor of O .

Now assume the *stationarity* of (O, γ) . Recall that a *stationary* manifold (O, h) is of the form:

$$O = O_0 \times \mathbb{E} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbb{E} \approx \mathbb{R}$, O_0 is a connected manifold, and the tensor metric h is of the form;

$$\begin{aligned} h(\mathbf{z})r^*((\bar{\xi}, \tau_1, \tau_2), (\bar{\xi}', \tau_1', \tau_2'))h^*(\mathbf{z}) = \\ h^*(\bar{\xi}, \bar{\xi}') + h^*(\delta(\mathbf{z}), \bar{\xi})\tau_1' + h^*(\delta(\mathbf{z}), \bar{\xi}') - \beta(\mathbf{z})[\tau_1\tau_1' + \tau_2\tau_2'] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$\forall \mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{x}, t, \tau) \in O$ and $\bar{\zeta} = (\bar{\xi}, \tau_1, \tau_2) \in T_z O = T_z O_0 \times \mathbb{E}$, h^* a Riemannian tensor metric on O_0 , $\delta(x)$ a smooth vector field, and $\beta(x)$ a positive smooth scalar field on O_0 . In particular, h is not dependent on (t, τ) .

Recall that a partial variational amount for the metric tensor γ of O , is an infinitesimal amount of difference in γ as measured between a perturbed γ denoted by $\bar{\gamma}$ evaluated at the fields on the same positions $\Psi(\mathbf{z})$:

$$\delta\gamma = \bar{\gamma}(\Psi(\mathbf{z})) - \gamma(\Psi(\mathbf{z})) \quad (6)$$

the Lie derivative along the vector field that generates the coordinate transformation. The local version of the metric tensor variation denoted by $\delta^*\gamma$ is given by:

$$\delta^*\gamma = \bar{\gamma}(\Psi(\mathbf{z}^*)) - \gamma(\Psi(\mathbf{z})) \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{z}^* = \mathbf{z} + f(\mathbf{z})$. f is the vector field that generates a coordinate transformation. The two variations are related as:

$$\delta\gamma = \delta^*\gamma - f(\mathbf{z})\partial\gamma \quad (8)$$

so that the partial variation $\partial\gamma$, can be expressed as:

$$\partial\gamma = \frac{\delta\gamma - \delta^*\gamma}{f(\mathbf{z})} \quad (9)$$

By considering the volume element $\sqrt{|\gamma|}$ and a Taylor expansion of it to first order in the partial variation $\partial\gamma$, one obtains the following [3]:

$$\partial\gamma = \frac{\sqrt{|\gamma + \partial\gamma|} - \sqrt{|\gamma|}}{\frac{\partial\sqrt{|\gamma|}}{\partial\gamma}} + O([\partial\gamma]^2) \quad (10)$$

The amount $\partial\gamma$ is considered a random variation of the 2T Dp-brane field metric tensor γ since, by nature, inherent quantum fields on the manifold O , are probabilistic. Each variational $\partial\gamma$, propagates a different local 2T Dp-brane field metric tensor curvature and here, we postulate that this, in turn, corresponds to a distinct local physical field within the F-Theory landscape. In other words,

for a given value of $\partial\gamma$ denoted by $\langle\partial\gamma\rangle_v$, there corresponds a physical field given by Υ_v , giving the equivalence relation $\langle\partial\gamma\rangle_v \equiv \Upsilon_v$ for each possible $v \in \mathbb{R}$.

By stationarity of (O, γ) , $\partial\gamma = \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\Psi} = 0$. The following conditions then hold:

$$\frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial t} = 0, \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\tau} = 0, \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\mathbf{x}} = 0, \frac{\partial^2\gamma'}{\partial t^2} = 0, \frac{\partial^2\gamma'}{\partial\tau^2} = 0, \frac{\partial^2\gamma'}{\partial\mathbf{x}^2} = 0 \quad (11)$$

and correspondingly;

$$\frac{\partial\mathcal{R}}{\partial t} = 0, \frac{\partial\mathcal{R}}{\partial\tau} = 0, \frac{\partial\mathcal{R}}{\partial\mathbf{x}} = 0, \frac{\partial^2\mathcal{R}'}{\partial t^2} = 0, \frac{\partial^2\mathcal{R}'}{\partial\tau^2} = 0, \frac{\partial^2\mathcal{R}'}{\partial\mathbf{x}^2} = 0 \quad (12)$$

The variational form of (3) with respect to $\partial\gamma$ and $\partial\gamma'$ can be expressed as [14]:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial L}{\partial\Psi} \frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial\gamma} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\mathcal{R}} \frac{\partial\mathcal{R}}{\partial t} \partial\gamma - \frac{\partial L}{\partial\left(\frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial t}\right)} \frac{\partial\left(\frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial t}\right)}{\partial\gamma} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\mathcal{R}} \frac{\partial^2\mathcal{R}}{\partial t^2} \partial\left(\frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial t}\right) \\ & - \frac{\partial L}{\partial\left(\frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial\tau}\right)} \frac{\partial\left(\frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial\tau}\right)}{\partial\gamma} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\mathcal{R}} \frac{\partial^2\mathcal{R}}{\partial\tau^2} \partial\left(\frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\tau}\right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial\left(\frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial\mathbf{x}}\right)} \frac{\partial\left(\frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial\mathbf{x}}\right)}{\partial\mathcal{R}} \frac{\partial^2\mathcal{R}}{\partial\mathbf{x}^2} \partial\left(\frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\mathbf{x}}\right) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

We now investigate variations of γ as local variations of families of curvatures of (O, γ) via Levi-Civita connections ∇ , where $\nabla\gamma = 0$, as a means of the manifestation of 2T Dp-brane fields, leading to simple SM bosonic and fermionic fields [2]. In the proceeding, we roughly follow [12] in generalizing to this 2T Dp-brane field metric tensor variation-based proposal. To do this, we first discretize the 2T Dp-brane field metric tensor γ into separate components $\partial\gamma_i$ whose representational values are mapped to a subset of \mathbb{P} , the primes.

Other recent efforts have been made to analogize and map \mathbb{P} to Standard Model (SM) particle representations using number-theoretic and group geometric properties of the division algebras $\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{Q}$, and \mathbb{H} , that may represent particle landscapes, and in the hopes of simplifying particle creation/annihilation processes [11]. Here, we directly analogize metric tensor variations and hence local manifold curvatures, with more general field landscapes. These variations will be mapped to a subset of \mathbb{P} and then to field creation caricature proxies. In this way, mathematical structures within \mathbb{P} serve as proxy models for field creation/annihilation. No claims to actual physical representations will be made outside of the 2T Dp-brane F-Theory manifolds that have been investigated in mathematical physics and continue to be important post signs of future development in quantum gravity.

Metric Tensor and Curvature Variations

Consider partitioning and discretizing (in effect, quantizing) $\partial\gamma$ into a series of distinct random variations $\partial\gamma_i$ and express it as an infinite sum of such variations

thereof;

$$\partial\gamma = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \partial\gamma_i = 0 \quad (14)$$

The partial sums of (9) as N -tuple approximations to $\partial\gamma$, are denoted by:

$$[\partial\gamma]_N = \sum_{i=1}^N \partial\gamma_i \quad (15)$$

Now consider permutations of the N -tuples $\{\partial\gamma_i\}_1^N$ that result in the same summation value $[\partial\gamma]_N$. Each N -tuple in the summation $[\partial\gamma]_N$ is equivalenced by the modulo operator that refers to the (net variation) value of $[\partial\gamma]_N$. We denote this N -tuple class by $[\cdot]_{[\partial\gamma]_N}$ giving rise to the dependence on the number of variations in the series N , and the value of the partial sum $[\partial\gamma]_N$. The set of permutations of this set is the group $\text{Sym}(\{\partial\gamma_i\}_1^N)$. One has as the order of this group $|\text{Sym}(\{\partial\gamma_i\}_1^N)| = N!$. The equivalence class $[\cdot]_{[\partial\gamma]_N}$ may also be considered as a permutation group with permutation mappings as the group actions.

Denote the zero equivalence class by $[0]_{[\partial\gamma]_N}$. In this regard, one selects N so

that the tail sum $\sum_{i=N+1}^{\infty} \partial\gamma_i \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$ faster than a rate commensurate

with field detection. One then considers permutations of $\{\partial\gamma_i\}_1^N$ such that the tail sum vanishes at a high rate:

$$\sum_{i=N+1}^{\infty} \partial\gamma_i = o\left(\frac{1}{N^l}\right), \text{ for some } l > 1 \quad (16)$$

Further to this analysis, one may assume that the distinct variation components forming the partial sum $[\partial\gamma]_N$ can take values from the set $\mathbb{K} = \{\pm \frac{\kappa}{K}, \kappa \in \{1, \dots, K\}\}$ for some possible variation normalizer value $K \in \mathbb{N}$. These values correspond to quasiparticle fractional charge-like magnitudes as multiples of $\frac{\kappa}{K}$ [15] [13]. In this case, the set of group actions on $\text{Sym}(\{\partial\gamma_i\}_1^N)$ consists of distinct compositions of the component identity mappings $e_i : \partial\gamma_i \rightarrow \partial\gamma_i$, and the K opposite sign component mappings $\rho_i : \partial\gamma_i \rightarrow -\partial\gamma_i$. The number of distinct permutations in the set $\{\partial\gamma_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N}$ is $(2K)^N$. Then $|\text{Sym}(\{\partial\gamma_i\}_1^N)| = (2K)^N$. Note also in this case, that from stationarity, $[\partial\gamma]_N \approx 0$, implying $N = 2k, k \in \mathbb{N}$ (i.e., the number of variation components in the partial sum $[\partial\gamma]_N$, is even under manifold stationarity). One may also model these permutations by the $\text{SU}(K)$ group reminiscent of Gell-Mann's and Zweig's Eightfold method of quark representations [18].

Now consider enumerating the combinations that produce the equivalence class values $[\partial\gamma_i]_1^N$. Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and count the number of combinations $\{\partial\gamma_i\}_1^N$, such

that $[\partial\gamma_i]_1^N = k$ for $\partial\gamma_i \in \mathbb{K}$:

$$\begin{aligned} |[\cdot]_k| &= C(k, N) \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^N \binom{N}{r} \binom{k+r-1}{N-1} \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^N 2^r \binom{N}{r} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

In particular, for $k = 0$, the zero variation for $\partial\gamma$:

$$\begin{aligned} |[\cdot]_0| &= C(0, N) \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^N 2^r \binom{N}{r} \binom{-1}{r-1} \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^N 2^r \binom{N}{r} (-1)^{r-1} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

So that, the number of combinations producing nonzero variations (i.e., $k \neq 0$) is;

$$\begin{aligned} |[\cdot]_k|_{k \neq 0} &= C(k, N)_{k \neq 0} \\ &= \sum_{k \neq 0} C(k, N) \\ &= (2K)^N - \sum_{r=0}^N 2^r \binom{N}{r} (-1)^{r-1} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

We next define the net variations as prime integers of the form:

$$v_{net}(m) = 2m + 1, m \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, 2m + 1 \in \mathbb{P} \quad (20)$$

where $m \not\equiv 0 \pmod{n}$ for some invariant positive integer $0 < n \leq N$, and \mathbb{P} is the set of primes.

Let \mathbb{NV} denote the set of all ordered (ascension) net variation numbers and denote the m -th element in \mathbb{NV} by p_m . Now consider the subset of net variation pairs of neighbors $(p_{m-1}, p_m) \in \mathbb{NV}^2$ such that $(p_{m-1} + p_m) \equiv 0 \pmod{Kn}$ for $K \in \mathbb{N}$, the number of distinct magnitudes for the component variations $\partial\gamma_i$. Denote this subset by \mathbb{NV}_{Kn}^2 . The total random variations from \mathbb{NV}_{Kn}^2 up to the m -th, can then be calculated by an induction in the following way:

Theorem: For $m \in \mathbb{N}$, the total random variations from \mathbb{NV}_{Kn}^2 , yielding net variations up to the m -th is given by:

$$v_{tot}(m, n, K) = \left[(2K)^n \prod_{i=1}^m p_i + n \right] + p_m \quad (21)$$

where $n =$ invariant number of variations $\leq N$, and $K =$ number of possible distinct magnitudes for the component variations. In [12], $n = 3$, $K = 1$, and $N = 4$.

Next, for each $m \in \mathbb{N}$, form the ratios

$$\alpha_v(m, n, K) = \frac{v_{\text{tot}}(m-1, n, K)}{v_{\text{tot}}(m, n, K)} \quad (22)$$

The ratios $\alpha_v(m, n, K)$ are considered to be the local relative (variational) strengths or *coupling constant parameters* of the curvatures for the pair $(p_{m-1}, p_m) \in \mathbb{NV}_{Kn}^2$.

Variational Curvature Field Creation

The local variational nature of the 2T Dp-brane field metric tensor γ in O , bounded away from its extremal curvatures, leads one to postulate on the field dynamics in those regions. The amount of these variations approximated by $[\partial\gamma_i]_N$, is directly linked to a corresponding amount of Gaussian, Ricci or other more appropriate curvature variation for (O, γ) . The dynamics of the local Dp-brane at $\Psi(\mathbf{z})$ is fully described by its local curvature in O through its field metric tensor value $\gamma(\Psi(\mathbf{z}))$. The pair $(v_{\text{tot}}(m, n, K), \alpha_v(m, n, K))$ gives a representation for this manifest 2T Dp-brane field and its relative strength as a coupling constant parameter. We are thus prompted to the following:

Claim 1: For each $m \in \mathbb{N}$, when $v_{\text{net}}(m, n, K) > 0$, the pair $(v_{\text{net}}(m, n, K), \alpha_v(m, n, K))$, of a positive prime-numbered (from \mathbb{NV}_{Kn}) 2T Dp-brane metric tensor variation and the ratio of the net variation to the total variation, respectively, correspond to the manifestation of a force (bosonic) field type and its relative strength or coupling constant parameter respectively. This is considered a "push" or local (+) curvature variation for a 2T Dp-brane force (bosonic) field.

Claim 2: For each $m \in \mathbb{N}$, if the net variation $v_{\text{net}}(m, n, K) \approx 0$, then the pair $(v_{\text{net}}(m), \alpha_v(m, n, K))$, correspond to a flat or nearly flat 2T Dp-brane metric tensor curvature variation and a net variation to total variation ratio of $\alpha_v(m, n, K)$. In this case, a mass (fermionic) 2T Dp-brane field is manifested with relative strength (coupling constant parameter) $\alpha_v(m, n, K)$. This is considered a "pull" or local nearly zero metric tensor curvature variation for a 2T Dp-brane mass (fermionic) field.

Let the physical field corresponding to the approximating partial sum $[\partial\gamma_i]_1^N$ for $m, n, K, N \in \mathbb{N}$ by denoted by $\Upsilon_{m,n,K,N}$.

Corollary: For each $m, n, K, N \in \mathbb{N}$, with $n, m \leq N$,

$$[\partial\gamma_i]_1^N \equiv \begin{cases} \Upsilon_{m,n,K,N} \text{ bosonic,} & \text{when } v_{\text{net}}(m, n, K) \in \mathbb{N}\mathbb{V}_{Kn} \\ \Upsilon_{m,n,K,N} \text{ fermionic,} & \text{when } v_{\text{net}}(m, n, K) = 0 \text{ } (N = 2k, k \in \mathbb{N}) \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

with coupling constant $\alpha_v(m, n, K)$.

Note that since $n, p_m, p_{m-1} \ll (2K)^n \rho_m$, where $\rho_m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i$, and for m large enough, then $\alpha_v(m, n, K) \approx \frac{\rho_{m-1}}{\rho_m} = \frac{1}{p_m} \ll o\left(\frac{1}{m \log(m)}\right)$ (using the prime number theorem), so that as would be expected, subsequent fields $\Upsilon_{m,n,K,N}$, as $m \rightarrow \infty$, have very weak to undetectable strengths through their nearly zero coupling constants.

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